

Metal Derivatives of Amidoximes VI¹. Synthesis of 1, 3, 5, 2-Oxadiazaboroles

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1, 3, 5, 2-Oxadiazaboroles of the types, $\text{R}(\text{HN})\text{C}=\text{NOB}-\text{OR}'$,
 $\text{R}(\text{HN})\text{C}=\text{NOB}-\text{ON}=\text{C}(\text{R})\text{NH}-\text{BON}=\text{C}(\text{NH})\text{R}$, $\text{R}(\text{HN})\text{C}=\text{NOB}$. Ph and
 $[\text{R}(\text{HN})\text{C}=\text{NOB}]_2-\text{O}$, (Where R = Me, Et, Pr or Ph and R' = Et or Pr^t)
 have been synthesized from the reactions of alkylborates, phenylboronic acid
 or boric acid with amidoximes and characterized.

1, 3, 5, 2-Oxadiazaboroles have not been reported². Only a brief mention of 2-phenyl- or 2-methoxy-1, 3, 5, 2-oxadiazaboroles derived from arylamidoximes, isonicotinamidoxime and pyridylamidoximes has been made.³⁻⁶ Boron heterocycles prepared from a number of amidoximes and benzamidoxime are described in the present paper.

Experimental

Precautions were taken to exclude moisture. Benzene, n-hexane, ethyl, isopropyl and t-butyl alcohols were dried by usual methods^{7, 17}. Alkyl borates were prepared from boric acid.¹⁸

Phenylboronic acid was prepared from PhMgBr and tributyl borate in equimolar ratio. Amidoximes were synthesized by standard methods^{20, 21}.

Boron was estimated by standard sodium hydroxide¹⁹ and nitrogen by Kjeldahl method. Alcohol in the azeotrope was estimated oxidimetrically.²² Molecular weights were determined ebullioscopically in benzene. I. r. spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer-337 instrument in the range of 4000-400 cm^{-1} on neat or on nujol using KBr plates. Proton n.m.r. spectra were recorded on HA 60 machine in CDCl_3 with TMS as internal standard. Thermogravimetric studies were done on Stanton thermobalance.

Experimental details of a representative reaction has been given below and the details of other reactions are given in Table 1 & 2.

Reaction between phenylboronic acid or boric acid or alkyl borate with amidoximes.

From the reaction mixture of boron compound and amidoxime, water or alcohol was fractionated out. The product was crystallized or distilled and analyzed.

Results and Discussion

Reactions of alkylborates, $\text{B}(\text{OR}')_3$ (R' = Et or Pr^t), with amidoximes, $\text{R}(\text{H}_2\text{N})\text{C}=\text{NOH}$ (R = Me, Et, Pr or Ph), in molar ratios 1 : 1, 2 : 3 or 1 : 2 in refluxing benzene resulted into products I, II or III respectively.

Reaction of isopropylborate with acetamidoxime, $\text{Me}(\text{H}_2\text{N})\text{C}=\text{NOH}$, in boiling xylene resulted in an insoluble product with a probable polymeric structure— $[\text{N}(\text{Me})\text{C}=\text{NOB}]_n$ —(IV). The reaction

of benzamidoxime, $\text{Ph}(\text{H}_2\text{N})\text{C}=\text{NOH}$, with isopropylborate in equimolar quantity in refluxing xylene, however, stops at the stage of the product (I, R = Ph and R' = Pr^t) and could not be pushed even after prolonged (—15h) refluxing which may be due to the greater steric effect of phenyl group.

Table-1

Reactions between Boric Acid or Phenylboronic Acid and Amidoximes
(Molar Ratios 1 : 1)

S. No.	Reactants (g)		Refluxed for (h)	Crystallised from (m.p.°C)	Product & Yield (%)	Analysis (%) Found (Calcd)	
	Boric acid or Phenyl boronic acid	Amidoxime R(H ₂ N)C : NOH R=				B	N
B(OH)₃							
1.	1.72	Me 2.05	8	—	$\left[\text{Me}(\text{HN})\text{C} = \text{NOB} \right]_2 - \text{O}$ 90	11.62 (11.76)	33.30 (30.48)
2.	1.42	Et 2.02	8	—	$\left[\text{Et}(\text{HN})\text{C} = \text{NOB} \right]_2 - \text{O}$ 94	10.14 (10.30)	26.40 (26.71)
3.	1.12	Pr 1.85	7	Benzene	$\left[\text{Pr}(\text{HN})\text{C} = \text{NOB} \right]_2 - \text{O}$ 92	9.01 (9.02)	23.36 (23.36)
4.	1.19	Ph 2.62	6	—	$\left[\text{Ph}(\text{HN})\text{C} = \text{NOB} \right]_2 - \text{O}$ 95	7.16 (7.22)	18.46 (18.72)
PhB(OH)₂							
5.	1.03	Me 0.63	8	Benzene (162-3)	$\text{Me}(\text{NH})\text{C} = \text{NOB} \cdot \text{Ph}^*$ 96	6.6 (6.7)	17.1 (17.5)
6.	1.00	Et 0.73	5	Benzene (122-3)	$\text{Et}(\text{HN})\text{C} = \text{NOB} \cdot \text{Ph}$ 94	6.08 (6.14)	15.80 (15.92)
7.	1.35	Pr 1.17	5	Benzene/n-hexane (100-1)	$\text{Pr}(\text{HN})\text{C} = \text{NOB} \cdot \text{Ph}$ 96	5.68 (5.75)	14.80 (14.89)
8.	1.42	Ph 1.60	4	Benzene (161-3)	$\text{Ph}(\text{HN})\text{C} = \text{NOB} \cdot \text{Ph}$ 98	4.84 (4.87)	12.52 (12.61)

All reactions were carried in benzene.

*, N,M,R,, Me, 7.6τ and Ph 2.0-2.5τ (multiplet).

Table-2

Reactions between Alkylborates and Amidoximes

S. No.	B(OPr ⁱ) ₃	RC $\begin{matrix} \text{NOH} \\ \diagup \\ \text{NH}_2 \end{matrix}$	Ratio	Refluxed for (h)	Product* and B.P. (°C/mm)	Yield (%)	Analysis alcohol in azeotrope (g)		
							B (%)	N (%)	Found (Calcd.) (%)
1.	2.79	Ph 2.03	1 : 1	6	$\text{Ph}(\text{HN})\text{C} = \text{NOB} \cdot \text{OPr}^i$ s, 140-5/0.2 (101-3)	(68)	1.62 (1.78)	5.15 (5.29)	13.70 (13.73)
2.	1.98	Me 0.78	1 : 1	10	$\text{Me}(\text{HN})\text{C} = \text{NOB} \cdot \text{OPr}^{i**}$ s, 100-10/0.5 (159-60)	(40)	1.25 (1.26)	7.51 (7.61)	19.66 (19.72)
3.	2.51	Et 1.18	1 : 1	6	$\text{Et}(\text{HN})\text{C} = \text{NOB} \cdot \text{OPr}^i$ 83.5/0.4	(65)	1.60 (1.61)	6.87 (6.93)	17.82 (17.96)
4.	3.06	Pr 1.66	1 : 1	7	$\text{Pr}(\text{HN})\text{C} = \text{NOB} \cdot \text{OPr}^i$ 94-6/0.2	(61)	1.90 (1.96)	6.18 (6.26)	16.40 (16.48)

TABLE-2 (CONTD.)

5.	2.08	Ph	2 : 3	5	Ph(HN)C = NOBON =CNHBON = C(NH)Ph d, 160-70/0.2	(95)	1.82 (1.99)	4.90 (4.97)	19.22 (19.32)
6.	3.80	Me	2 : 3	10	Me(HN)C = NOBON =CNHBON = C(NH)Me d. 150 - 5/0.2(120-2)	(96)	3.59 (3.65)	901 (9.09)	35.10 (35.32)
7.	2.28	Et.	2 : 3	6	Et(HN)C = NOBON =CNHBON = C(NH)Et 98-100/0.2	(71)	2.08 (2.19)	7.61 (7.69)	30.01 (30.02)
8.	1.76	Pr	2 : 3	6	Pr(HN)C = NOBON =CNHBON = C(NH)Pr s. 120 - 30/0.2	(60)	1.55 (1.69)	6.65 (6.71)	25.97 (26.10)
9.	2.09	Ph	1 : 2	5	Ph(HN)C = NOBON=C(NH ₂)Ph d.220 - 10/0.1 (161-2)	(96)	2.02 (2.02)	3.81 (3.86)	19.77 (20.00)
10.	2.07	Et	1 : 2	6	Et(HN)C = NOBON=C(NH ₂)Et d. 160 - 5/0.1	(97)	1.86 (1.98)	5.81 (5.88)	30.21 (30.45)
					B(OEt) ₃				
11.	3.43	Et	1 : 1	6	Et(HN)C=NOB.OEt 75-77/0.3	(68)	2.08 (2.17)	7.51 (7.61)	20.70 (20.72)
12.	3.71	Me	1 : 1	10	Me(HN)C = NOB.OEt s. 100-10/0.2 (147-8)	(55)	2.22 (2.34)	8.40 (8.45)	21.86 (21.91)
13.	2.76	Pr	1 : 1	6	Pr(HN)C = NOB.OEt 84-86/0.2	(70)	1.68 (1.74)	6.81 (6.93)	17.85 (17.96)
14.	2.72	Ph	1 : 1	6	Ph(HN)C = NOB.OEt s. 135-40/0.2 (94-5)	(72)	1.68 (1.71)	5.64 (5.69)	14.70 (14.74)
					R(HN)C = NOB.OPr ⁱ Bu ^t OH				
15.	R=Me 1.90	10.00	1 : excess	10	Me(HN)C = NOB. OBU ^t s. 100-10/0.2	(80)	0.75 (0.79)	6.90 (6.90)	17.80 (18.0)
16.	R=Et 2.12	4.01	1 : excess		Et(HN)C - NOB.OBU ^t (163-5)	(90)	0.78 (0.81)	6.32 (6.36)	16.32 (16.48)
17.	Pr 2.57	4.25	1 : excess		Pr(HN)C=NOB.OBU ^t Crystd. from benzene	(88)	0.88 (0.91)	5.81 (5.87)	15.04 (15.23)
18.	Ph 2.50	6.90	1 : excess		Ph(HN)C = NOB.OBU ^t s.130-40/0.1	(66)	0.70 (0.72)	4.92 (4.96)	12.66 (12.85)
19.	Ph 2.69	CH ₃ COOH 0.85	1 : 1	4	Ph(HN)C = NOB.OAc	(90)	0.61 (0.65)	5.20 (5.30)	13.60 (13.70)

*. Reactions were carried in benzene. s=Sublimation; d=Decomposition; M.P. in parenthesis
Data of reaction products (5, 6, 9 and 10) are before attempted distillation.

"A residue was left (Found : B, 12.76; N, 33.68; $\left[\begin{array}{c} \text{N(Me)C=NOB} \\ | \\ \text{N} \end{array} \right]_n$ Calcd. : B, 13.20; N, 34.22%)

** NMR, Me, 7.83 τ and (CH₃)₂C as doublet centred at 8.68 τ .

Alkoxy group of the products, $[R(HN)C=NOB-OR']$ (I; $R'=Et$ or Pr^t) can be replaced by tert-butoxy in alcoholysis and by acetato group to give (V and VI).

(V; $R=Me, Et, Pr$ or Ph)

(VI; $R=Ph$)

Compounds 2-phenyl-3-hydro-4-alkyl- or 4-phenyl-1, 3, 5, 2-oxadiazaboroles (VII) and 2, 2-oxybis(3-hydro-4-alkyl- or 4-phenyl-1, 3, 5, 2-oxadiazaboroles) (VIII) have been synthesized by the azeotropic removal of water with benzene from an equimolar mixture of phenylboronic acid or boric acid and the appropriate amidoximes.

(VII)

(VIII) ($R=Me, Et, Pr$ or Ph)

Products I, II and V are white sublimable unimolecular solids or distillable viscous liquids. The products $Me(HN)C=NOB-OR'$ ($R'=Et$ or Pr^t)

undergo sublimation under reduced pressure in relatively poor yields (40-50%) with disproportion to yield the product (IV). Compounds III are white solids recrystallizable from hot THF/benzene. Compounds VII are white solids monomeric in refluxing benzene. Boric acid derivatives (VIII) are white solids insoluble in benzene and have been used for the preparation of 2-(trialkylstannoxy)- and 2-(trimethylsiloxy)3-hydro-4-alkyl-1, 3, 5, 2-oxadiazaboroles⁷.

Infrared spectra

In the i. r. spectra of all the compounds the strong band in the region $3570-3650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to $\nu(OH)$ of the parent amidoximes⁸ is found to be absent. The νNH_2 bands observed in the regions $3480-3500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $3330-3400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (in the amidoximes) are replaced in compounds by a single peak in the regions $3230-3320\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (in I, II, V, VI and VIII) and $3160-3220\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (in VII; $R=Me$ or

Pr) and 3375 cm^{-1} (in VII; $R=Ph$) assignable to $\nu(NH)$. In cyclic compounds of phosphorus similar changes have been reported by Barrans *et. al.*⁹ Characteristic i. r. bands are observed for $\nu C=N$ in region $1625-1675\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\nu N-O$ at $920 \pm 10\text{ cm}^{-1}$. An unassignable strong band is observed in spectra of all the compounds at $\sim 1545\text{ cm}^{-1}$. In compounds I and V, the stretching vibrations due to C-O of alkoxy groups are observed in the regions $1040-1120$ and $1170-1190\text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively^{10,12}.

In I, V, VII and VIII stretching vibration due to B-N has been observed at $\sim 1500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\nu B-O$ absorption has apparently fallen from 1350 cm^{-1} (in $B(OR)_3$ ¹³) to $1320 \pm 10\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (due to B-O(N) and 1280 cm^{-1} (due to B-O(X)). These indicate a lowering of bond order in the B-O links and increase of B-N bond order; this would be expected owing to strong nitrogen to boron back-coordination^{14,15} suggesting the structure.

In (VI) the absence of any band above 1670 cm^{-1} (free carbonyl absorbs at 1708 cm^{-1} in acetate¹⁶) indicates the possibility of structure shown (VI). This finds support from the $\nu B-N$ which shifts to lower region from 1500 cm^{-1} . The product (III; $R=Ph$) exhibits a doublet in i. r. spectrum at 3400 and 3300 cm^{-1} due to νNH_2 lowered by about 90 cm^{-1} in comparison to the parent benzamidoxime¹⁷ indicating internal coordination; this also shows shifting of $\nu B-N$ to lower region. The four-coordinate boron structure for (III) is further supported by its non-reactivity with pyridine or triethylamine.¹⁸

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